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Parametric analysis and optimization by means of DoE techniques of a building insulation coating for façade renovation

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Abstract

The energetic performance of a building insulation coating is assessed by means of simulations of a dynamic RC model and by carrying out a parametric analysis based on Design of Experiment techniques.

The external insulation coating is characterized by three parameters: the thermal conductive resistance, the shortwave solar absorptivity, and the longwave emissivity. The façade of the building is modelled with two lumped thermal capacitances on the internal and the external surfaces, and two thermal resistances representing the conduction through the wall and the internal convective and radiative phenomena. The external insulation is modelled by two more thermal resistances, which simulate the external convective exchanges and the conduction through the insulation, and one thermal capacitance in the insulation external surface. The inputs to the model are the external ambient temperature, the internal temperature, and the weather conditions (the wind convective heat transfer coefficient and the incident shortwave and the longwave radiative heat fluxes).

The analyzed output parameter of the model is the internal surface heat flux, which has a direct impact on the heating and cooling loads. The Box-Behnken Design has been used to select the optimal values of the parameters of the insulation coating that result in a maximized internal heat flux during winter months and a minimized flux during summer months. The use of the Box-Behnken Design permits to assess the combined effect of the input parameters on the output parameter and the formulation of a simplified compact model to predict the latter as a function of the formers.

The outcomes of the models suggest that surface emissivity is a key factor in summer periods while winter periods are mostly dominated by the thermal resistance in the wall.

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1. Introduction

Energy efficient buildings have become an increasingly common issue, due to the growing demand to satisfy not only economic and social but also more ambitious environmental requirements.

According to Loonen et al (2013), two alternative directions have been taken during these years to design low-energy consuming buildings: active and passive technologies. The active strategies are focussed in providing, for instance, renewable energy, so that a cleaner consumption is favoured. The passive alternatives, on the other hand, are related with the design and shape of the building itself. These techniques have an important role on capturing, storing, and distributing solar energy and wind. Building insulation coatings (in which this paper is focused) and adaptive envelopes are two passive technologies which are playing an important role in new constructions but also in the renovation of façades (Ascione et al (2013) and Santos et al (2020)).

It has been proved that the retrofit of the building envelope contributes to high energy savings. The research work presented in this paper aims to assess the energetic performance of a building insulation coating for façade renovation.

The thermal performance of a wall of a building has been simulated by means of a dynamic RC model in section 2. Three parameters have been used to characterize the external coat or envelope: the thermal conductive resistance, the shortwave solar absorptivity, and the longwave emissivity. In section 3, by using Design of Experiment (DoE) techniques, a parametric analysis of these variables has been carried out to find out which are the optimum values for the variables that represent the insulation coating of the building in terms of energy efficiency. The key parameter used as indicator of this efficiency has been the internal surface heat flux, which has a direct impact on the heating and cooling loads. The inputs of the model have been the external ambient temperature, the internal temperature, and the weather conditions. The analysis has been carried out for three different types of walls under the weather conditions of Bilbao (North of Spain).

The programming and numeric computing platform Matlab has been used for describing the dynamic RC model that characterises the wall. For implementing the Design of Experiments, the statistical analysis software Minitab has been used (Mathews (2005)).

Altogether this paper proposes a new way to define the configuration of a building façade considering thermal conduction across insulation materials, as well as surface radiation phenomena in its outer layer. By doing so, it may enable the identification of new techno-economical optimal solutions for the configuration of building envelopes in the context of Nearly Zero Energy Buildings.

2. Description of the model

The wall of the building can be represented as an RC model shown in Figure 1. It can be characterized by two capacitances (C_{me} and C_{mi}) and two resistances (R_m and R_{mi}), which will be explained below. The external insulation coating (or external envelope) of the façade is modeled by a capacitance (C_{mout}) and a thermal resistance (R_{out}), which represents the thickness of the layer that is being attached in the exterior. The resistance in the left (R_{se}) (see Figure 1) is related to convective phenomena.

Fig. 1. RC model of the heat transfer interaction through the wall and the insulation coating.

2.1. Input parameters

2.1.1. Boundary conditions

The external and internal air temperatures (T_e and T_i), as well as the short and long wave incident radiations ($Q_{e,sw}$ and $Q_{e,lw}$) are considered as boundary conditions, and their values are obtained and calculated from the climatic dataset of Bilbao.

2.1.2. Characteristics of the façade

The capacitors and resistances that are shown in Figure 1 and are needed to model the system are obtained from the climatic dataset of Bilbao and from the dataset of the thermophysical properties of the different materials of the façades.

2.2. Capacitors

The capacitors represent the external and internal capacitance of the wall (thermal capacitance lumped to the external surface of the wall, C_{me} , thermal capacitance lumped to the internal surface of the wall, C_{mi} , and the one lumped to the external coating of the façade, C_{mout} [$J/m^2 \cdot K$]). The values of C_{me} and C_{mi} change depending on the façade which is being analysed.

The next assumption will be made during the calculations: the value of C_{mout} will be omitted from the model ($C_{mout} = 0$) as it is insignificant compared to the values of C_{me} and C_{mi} .

2.3. Resistances

R_m [$m^2 \cdot K/W$] represents the thermal resistance of the wall, which also changes depending on the façade studied.

The external thermal resistance, R_{se} , is related to convective phenomena, with a variable value that depends on the wind velocity and the wind direction.

R_{out} is the thermal resistance of the external insulation of the wall. It models the effect of covering the building with an external skin (building envelope).

The internal superficial resistance, R_{mi} , encompasses not only convective phenomena, but radiant. An estimation of its value, 0.125 [$m^2 \cdot K/W$], can be taken from Zirkelbach et al (2017) a software which determines the hygrothermal performance of building components under real climate conditions.

2.4. States

The superficial exterior and interior temperatures of the wall (T_{me} and T_{mi}), as well as the envelope's superficial temperature (T_{env}), are obtained from the model for each time step. They are the unknowns that will be calculated.

2.5. Outputs of interest

From Equation (1), the model allows to calculate the value of the heat flux (Q_{mi}) [W/m^2] from the inside surface of the wall. This heat flux can be used as an indicator of the thermal influence of the wall (heat interaction between the façade and the climatized space) per surface unit. A positive value means heat gain to the inside while a negative sign represents heat loss. In Section 3, this variable will be used as an energy optimization parameter of the building.

$$Q_{mi} = \frac{T_{mi} - T_i}{R_{mi}} \quad (1)$$

2.6. Equations of the model

From the RC model of the system presented in Figure 1 the following three differential equations (2-4) characterizing the heat transfer in the system can be deduced:

$$C_{mout} \frac{dT_{env}}{dt} = \frac{T_e - T_{env}}{R_{se}} + \frac{T_{me} - T_{env}}{R_{out}} + Q_{e,sw} + Q_{e,lw} \quad (2)$$

$$C_{me} \frac{dT_{me}}{dt} = \frac{T_{env} - T_{me}}{R_{out}} + \frac{T_{mi} - T_{me}}{R_m} \quad (3)$$

$$C_{mi} \frac{dT_{mi}}{dt} = \frac{T_{me} - T_{mi}}{R_m} + \frac{T_i - T_{mi}}{R_{mi}} \quad (4)$$

To integrate these differential equations numerically, a temporal discretization has been done, where the temperatures in two consecutive time steps have been considered, T_{env} y $T_{env,prev}$. To solve these equations (in which the only unknowns are T_{env} , T_{me} and T_{mi}) numerical calculations are needed. In this case, the programming and numeric computing platform *Matlab* has been used.

3. Design of Experiments (DoE)

3.1. Introduction

In a building, there are several parameters that do affect the heat interaction between the exterior and the interior. To analyse how these variables can have an effect on the energy efficiency of the building, a parametric analysis and an optimization have been carried out by means of Design of Experiments (DoE, Montgomery (2015)) techniques.

The three input parameters that model the attached external insulation coating are:

- R_{out} (thermal resistance of the outer coating) [$m^2 \cdot K/W$]. It is the resistance that models the effect of covering the building with a skin (building insulation) of a certain thickness. In this project, the values that this resistance will take are limited: (0.01 - 5) [$m^2 \cdot K/W$].
- Epsilon (ε or ε_{lw}) (long-wave emissivity of external surface), [-]. Emissivity values in the range of 0.4 to 0.9 are tested, in agreement with reference values for reflective (0.4) and common (0.9) materials for in Incropera et al. (2017).
- Alpha (α or α_{se}) (short-wave absorptivity of external surface), [-]. It represents the fraction of the incident solar radiative energy absorbed by the material. An alpha value range between 0.2 and 0.8 are tested in line with reference values for high reflectance (0.2) and dark (0.8) surfaces in Incropera et al (2017).

To analyse the energy efficiency of the building Q_{mi} has been selected as the representative output, which has been divided in the following two output parameters:

- $Q_{mi,summer.mean}$: mean value of the values of $Q_{mi,summer}$ during the hours (time steps) that constitute the summer period [W/m^2].
- $Q_{mi,winter.mean}$: mean value of the values of $Q_{mi,winter}$ during the hours that constitute the winter period [W/m^2].

The summer period considered is from May to October and winter period from November to April (with the months mentioned included, respectively).

The objective of this analysis is to find out which are the optimum characteristics of the insulation coating that will end up in a decreasing energy consumption of the building. These solutions will vary for the different weather conditions corresponding to the place the studied building is located, as well as for different materials used in the façade of the building.

As it has been said, in this work, the location, orientation and other needed characteristics are obtained from the weather file of Bilbao. When it comes to the façade of the building, a total of three façades will be observed to contrast how the solutions vary: a solid concrete façade, a brick wall with chamber and no thermal insulation, and finally, a brick wall with chamber and thermal insulation. The values considered for the above mentioned input parameters (R_{out} , ε and α) for each specific wall have been obtained from the Zirkelbach et al (2017).

Before identifying the method that best fits this concrete problem, two designs have been tried: Faced-Centred Central Composite Design (CCF) and Box-Behnken Design, to finally select this second one as the most appropriate one.

Three optimality tests have been carried out for each of the analysed façades: a combined optimization, and two individual optimizations (one to maximize Q_{mi} during winter months and the other to minimize Q_{mi} during summer months).

3.2. Combined optimization

The first optimization consists of finding a unique configuration of the parameters that constitute the external insulation coating so that both objectives are reached at the same time: maximizing Q_{mi} during winter and minimizing it during summer. The optimal solutions obtained for each façade are presented in Figure 2.

Optimal Combination of Parameters		Optimal Combination of Parameters		Optimal Combination of Parameters	
Rout [$m^2 \cdot K/W$]	3.33667	Rout [$m^2 \cdot K/W$]	3.5887	Rout [$m^2 \cdot K/W$]	4.3447
Epsilon	0.9	Epsilon	0.9	Epsilon	0.9
Alpha	0.2	Alpha	0.2	Alpha	0.2

Fig. 2. Optimal combination of parameters for the concrete façade (a), brick wall with chamber and no thermal insulation (b) and brick wall with chamber and thermal insulation (c).

When the combined optimization is performed, the three different analyzed façades coincide in the parameters that represent the external insulation coating, that is, in the emissivity and absorptivity values (0.9 and 0.2, respectively). To understand this, the Pareto Charts, which show the significance that each parameter has in the responses, as well as the Main Effects Plots, need to be analysed. The concrete façade will be studied below (Figures 3 and 4) to then explain which are the main differences in respect to the remaining two façades, which result in the optimal values for the thermal resistance (Rout) going from around $3.34 m^2 \cdot K/W$ (for the concrete wall) to $4.34 m^2 \cdot K/W$ (for the brick wall with chamber and thermal insulation) (see Figure 2).

Fig. 3. Pareto Charts for the concrete façade in the winter (a) and summer (b) response.

The charts for the concrete façade are presented above, but the remaining two façades show a similar distribution. It can be concluded that the emissivity (Epsilon) is not significant for either response, and could therefore be omitted from the analysis.

During winter, the resistance appears to be the most significant parameter (Fig 3.a).

During summer, the absorptivity is the most important variable (Fig 3.b), where a low value is preferable (Figure 4c and 4d), being highly dependent to Rout in this concrete façade (see Figures 3b and 4d), but not that much in other façades, as it will be shown.

The reason of the strange curve that Rout presents (Fig 4a and 4c) can have the answer in the Pareto Charts above presented (Fig3b). It has been said how dependent this variable is during summer to the value that the absorptivity takes. Therefore, even though Rout is the most important parameter during winter, alpha is essential during summer, so a maximum value for the resistance is not recommended if both opposing objectives are desired (as high values of Rout negatively affect summer months). This is the reason why the two first analyzed façades give an optimal value

of around $3.5 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K}/\text{W}$ for Rout. However, when the last façade is observed, the optimal Rout value gets closer to the maximum allowed value (Figure 2c), what makes sense if the Pareto Charts of the three façades are compared (Fig 5).

Fig. 4. Main Effects and Interaction Plots for the concrete façade in the winter (a, b) and summer (c, d) response.

Fig. 5. Pareto Charts during summer for the concrete façade (a), brick wall with chamber and no thermal insulation (b) and brick wall with chamber and thermal insulation (c).

The interaction of Rout with alpha (AC in Fig 5) is not that significant during summer response in this last façade (Fig 5c) as it was in the previous ones. Therefore, there is more freedom to choose the most appropriate Rout value for winter months without having to worry how it would affect summer months.

3.2.1. Conclusions

The coating in the combined optimization would present low absorptivity, not to store heat coming from the Sun, and high emissivity, regardless of the analysed façade. Note that a high emissivity would contribute to lower values of Q_{mi} (as it is a property of reflective materials) which will reject the radiation coming from the Sun (so less heat flux entering the building).

Depending on the façade that is being studied, R_{out} will preferably reach higher or lower values.

Figure 6 shows in grey the values that the response Q_{mi} would take with the insulation coating obtained in the combined optimization (in the concrete façade).

Fig. 6. $Q_{mi} \left[\frac{W}{m^2} \right]$ in the combined optimization of the concrete façade during a year.

3.3. Independent optimizations

The optimal configurations obtained in the individual theoretical optimizations for summer and winter months for each façade are presented in Fig 7.

a)	Optimal Combination of Parameters		b)	Optimal Combination of Parameters		c)	Optimal Combination of Parameters	
	For maximizing Q_{mi} [W/m ²] during winter	For minimizing Q_{mi} [W/m ²] during summer		For maximizing Q_{mi} [W/m ²] during winter	For minimizing Q_{mi} [W/m ²] during summer		For maximizing Q_{mi} [W/m ²] during winter	For minimizing Q_{mi} [W/m ²] during summer
Rout [m ² ·K/W]	4.5968	0.01	Rout [m ² ·K/W]	3.3871	0.01	Rout [m ² ·K/W]	3.7399	0.01
Epsilon	0.4	0.9	Epsilon	0.4	0.9	Epsilon	0.4	0.9
Alpha	0.2	0.2	Alpha	0.8	0.2	Alpha	0.8	0.2

Fig. 7. Optimal combination of parameters for the concrete façade (a), brick wall with chamber and no thermal insulation (b) and brick wall with chamber and thermal insulation (c).

If summer months are observed, the same optimum configuration has been given for the three façades. As it happened in the combined optimization, high emissivity and low absorptivity are preferable to minimize the heat entering the building (reflective coating). When it comes to the R_{out} value, the lowest possibility has been selected (what implies a thin coating) what can be shocking if Q_{mi} is desired to be minimized. The explanation of it can be found in Figure 6 above. During summer, Q_{mi} , which has been presented in Figure 1 as an entering heat flux, is in fact escaping from the inside (negative values in Figure 6). Therefore, the more Q_{mi} is favoured to escape from the interior the better (the thinner the coating the better).

During winter months, however, the configuration differs from one façade to others. The Pareto Charts of the winter responses need to be analysed to understand why (Fig 8).

Fig. 8. Pareto Charts for winter response for the concrete façade (a), brick wall with chamber and no thermal insulation (b) and brick wall with chamber and thermal insulation (c).

When the absorptivity is being observed, despite in the concrete façade it appears to be a practically insignificant value, in the remaining two façades it gains more significance (as the bars extend further from the red line). However, it is still the resistance the variable with the highest impact in the winter response of the three façades. It can be clearly observed how in the concrete façade a high value of R_{out} is selected (Fig 7a), whereas in the remaining façades the interaction of R_{out} with α is more significant (Fig 8b and c) so an equilibrium between them must be accomplished, resulting in a lower resistance but higher absorptivity (Fig 7b and c).

3.3.1. Conclusions

During summer months, the optimal configuration would be the same for the three façades: a reflective coating (to prevent the heat from the Sun entering the building) with the lowest resistance possible (to contribute to the heat exit to the exterior).

During winter months, the optimal configuration depends on the façade analysed. The most significant variable in the three façades is the resistance (being the emissivity practically insignificant in all of them). Whereas in the concrete façade the impact that the absorptivity has is as well practically negligible (a random value of 0.4 has been given) it is essential in the remaining two façades (opting for a high value which would positively contribute to the heat store inside the building and in a decreasing need to make the resistance that big).

4. Conclusions

Three main conclusions have been taken out from the results observed. Firstly, the important role that the insulation (specially during winter) plays has been remarked. Secondly, the absorptivity seems to be really significant during summer, opting for the lowest value possible. Finally, this work has confirmed the positive contribution of reflective coating building envelopes for energy savings.

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